

STABILITY AND ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL OF STANNIC OXIDE SOL

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The values of ζ_a has been calculated by using Smoluchowski's equation from electro-osmotic and electrophoretic data on stannic oxide sol in the region of slow coagulation in presence of the chlorides of Na^+ , Ba^{2+} , Al^{3+} and $\text{CO}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{2+}$. The specific conductivity 'S' of the supernatant solution in equilibrium with the coagulum has also been measured. A plot of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/S$ yields a straight line which makes an intercept ($1/\zeta$) on the $1/\zeta_a$ axis. This ' ζ ' has been identified with the true electrokinetic potential of the sol in presence of the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes mentioned above. The average value of true ' ζ ' potential determined by the electrophoretic and electro-osmotic methods of the given stannic oxide sol under the conditions mentioned above is equal to -37.0 mv.

Attempts have previously been made to correlate the stability of colloids with the electrical charge of their particles or the potential of the double layer surrounding them. Hardy's theory (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1900, **66A**, 110; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **33**, 385) of isoelectric precipitation or Powis's theory (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, **89**, 186) of a critical coagulation potential may be cited as examples. In recent years it has been shown that the true value of the electrokinetic potential cannot be found from the electrophoretic or the electro-osmotic data using Smoluchowski's equation. In a series of papers (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 955; 1953, **49**, 1477; this *Journal*, 1953, **30**, 9) Ghosh and co-workers have shown that the true value of electrokinetic potential can be found from the equation:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ζ_a = apparent electrokinetic potential calculated from Smoluchowski's equation, 'S' = specific conductivity of the supernatant solution, ζ = true electrokinetic potential and for electro-osmosis

$$m = 3V_1/V_2 \cdot (\chi/\zeta_a)$$

and for electrophoresis $m = \chi/\zeta_a$, where χ is the specific surface conductance of the colloidal particles, 'r' is its radius and V_1/V_2 is the ratio of the volume of the solid particles to that of liquid in the diaphragm. Ghosh and co-workers by using the above equation have determined the true values of ' ζ ' potential of sols of As_2S_3 , TiO_2 and AgI (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 1477; 1954, **50**, 379; *Science & Culture*, 1953, **10**, 498) in the presence of equicoagulating concentration of various electrolytes. They have arrived at the conclusion that a given rate of coagulation of a colloid is characterised by a definite

value of its true ' ζ ' potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used. It may be pointed out that their conclusion differs from that of Powis, since the former authors correlate the rate of coagulation with the electrokinetic potential, while the latter assumes that coagulation of a colloid can start when its electrokinetic potential falls below a certain critical value. In this paper the results of investigation on the stability and the electrokinetic potential of stannic oxide sol have been recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Colloid.—Negatively charged stannic oxide sol was prepared by Zsigmondy's method (*Annalen*, 1898, 301, 361). To a 20% solution of stannic chloride in conductivity water liquor ammonia was added dropwise till it became alkaline and set to a gel. The gel was first washed by decantation with distilled water and finally in a Büchner funnel till it was free from chloride ion. The oxide was then dispersed in conductivity water by shaking and peptised by using a centinormal solution of ammonia. The coarse suspension was allowed to stand for 18 hours and the supernatant sol was separated from the sediment by decantation. The excess ammonia in the sol was driven out by bubbling CO₂-free air through it, followed by dialysis. The dialysis was carried out for nearly a month. The sol obtained in this way was very dilute and pure. The amount of ammonia per 100 c.c. of the sol was 0.004023 g., indicating that most of the ammonia originally used had been removed. Its stannic oxide content was 0.74% and the specific conductivity was 1.22×10^{-4} mhos at 35°.

Determination of the Equicoagulating Concentration.—In these experiments, an electrolyte solution (2 c.c.) was mixed with 2 c.c. of the colloid and the mixture left as such for 20 hours. After this period the mixture was centrifuged exactly for 2 minutes under a regulated speed. The supernatant liquid was then examined for transparency or opacity. The equicoagulating concentration was such that the supernatant liquid became just transparent after centrifugation.

Measurement of Electrokinetic Potential by the Electro-osmotic Method.—The coagula were obtained by adding a definite volume of an electrolyte solution to an equal volume of the colloid. This was maintained constant in all the experiments. The final concentration of the electrolyte in the mixture represents its equicoagulating concentration. The coagula were separated from the bulk by centrifuging and were transferred with a small amount of the supernatant liquid into a 'U' tube. The diaphragm was prepared in the 'U' tube by centrifuging for a definite period. The volume occupied by the coagula was maintained constant in all the experiments. The supernatant liquid, obtained from the colloid-electrolyte mixture, was used for filling the 'U' tube and for the measurement of the specific conductance. The electrokinetic potential of the coagula of stannic oxide sol at the equicoagulating concentration of various electrolytes was measured in an apparatus similar to that used by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Nature*, 1922, 110, 732). The electro-osmotic experiments were carried out at 35°. The value of ' D ' used was 74 and had been calculated from the empirical equation, $D = 80 - 0.4(t - 20)$. The electrokinetic potentials were measured by duplicate experiments and the extent of reproducibility of the results was found to be within $\pm 3\%$.

Measurement of ζ_a by the Electrophoretic Method.—For the determination of ζ_a by

FIG. 1

electrophoresis, a modified form of Burton's apparatus was used. It consists of a 'U' tube, each limb of which was provided with a cup at the top and a stop-cock at the middle, the bore of the stop-cocks and the limbs being the same. Into the bottom of the 'U' tube was sealed a capillary tube bent upward and carried a tap at the middle and a funnel at the upper end. The concentration of electrolyte was so chosen as to cause coagulation in 20 hours. Hence, when the colloid was mixed with an electrolyte solution, only a slight precipitation occurred in 30 minutes. The colloid-electrolyte mixture was allowed to stand for 30 minutes and then the mixture was freed from the precipitates by centrifuging for 2 minutes. The lower part of the 'U' tube and also the bores of the stop-cocks were filled with this colloid-electrolyte mixture. The stop-cocks were then closed. The portion above the stop-cocks of the 'U' tube was then filled with the clear supernatant fluid, prepared from another lot of the colloid-electrolyte mixture having the same electrolyte concentration as the mixture. A clear intermicellar fluid was obtained by rapidly centrifuging the mixture after 20 hours of standing. Two Ag-AgCl electrodes in spiral forms were used and these were

dipped into the clear liquid to the same extent in each experiment. The reversible electrodes have been used to avoid electrolysis and thereby avoiding the fluctuation of current during the experiment. The level of the intermicellar fluid in the two limbs was always the same. The two stop-cocks were then opened cautiously so that the boundary between the colloid and the supernatant solution remained sharp. The tap in the the delivery tube was carefully opened in order to allow the boundary to rise in the vertical limb to a level about 2.5 cm above the stop-cocks and when the desired level was reached, it was closed.

Electric field was then applied and a controlled current, adjusted by suitable resistances, was allowed to flow. The time required by the boundary to travel 1 cm both in the upward and downward directions was noted and from this the electrophoretic velocities for upward and downward movements were calculated. The specific conductivities of the supernatant liquid and the colloid-electrolyte mixture differed to the extent of 4% only, when the coagulating concentration was very low, *i.e.*, in the cases of polyvalent electrolytes. Hence, an average of the specific conductivities of the supernatant liquid and the colloid-electrolyte mixture was used throughout in the calculation of potential gradient. The values of ζ_a have been calculated both for the upward and

downward movements of the boundary. Their average values are recorded in Table II. As in electro-osmosis the value of 'D' has been calculated from the empirical relation referred to previously. The electrophoretic experiments were carried out at room temperature which varied somewhat from day to day, the maximum range of variation not exceeding 3°. The specific conductivity, 'S', and the viscosity, η , have therefore been corrected for 25°, the average temperature, and since the product $S\eta$ remains constant and enters into the calculation of ζ_a , the latter is not affected by the correction thus made.

TABLE I

Electro-osmotic data for slow coagulation.

Time = 20 hours. Temp. = 35°

$$\zeta = -37.0 \text{ mv. } m = \frac{3V_1}{V_2} \cdot \frac{X}{\zeta_r} = 2.71 \times 10^{-8}$$

Electrolyte.	Equicoagulating conc.	Sp. condv. of supernatant soln. at 35°. (S × 10 ⁴)	Values of ζ_a calc. from Smoluchowski's equation (experimental).	Eqn. (1).
NaCl	$8.123 \times 10^{-3} N$	13.920	-34.3 mv	-34.5 mv
KCl	8.750×10^{-3}	15.430	-34.5	-31.7
NaCl } (I)	1.875×10^{-3}	4.351	-31.4	-30.1
& BaCl ₂	5.603×10^{-4}			
NaCl } (II)	8.123×10^{-4}	2.634	-26.5	-26.8
& BaCl ₂	7.003×10^{-4}			
BaCl ₂	8.004×10^{-4}	1.636	-22.9	-22.9
AlCl ₃	7.180×10^{-4}	1.823	-23.5	-23.9
CO(NH ₂) ₆ Cl ₃	8.034×10^{-4}	1.618	-22.0	-22.8

TABLE II

Electrophoretic data for slow coagulation.

Time = 20 hours. Temp. = 25°.

$$\zeta = -37.0 \text{ mv. } m = \frac{X}{\zeta_r} = 4.51 \times 10^{-7}$$

Electrolyte.	Equicoagulating conc.	Average sp. condv. of supernatant soln. and colloid-electrolyte mixture at 25°. (S × 10 ⁴).	Values of ζ_a calc. from Smoluchowski's eqn.		Average Experimental.	Eqn. (1)
			Upward.	Downward.		
NaCl	$8.123 \times 10^{-3} N$	9.696	-33.7 mv.	-33.9 mv.	-33.8 mv.	-36.4 mv.
NaCl } (I)	8.123×10^{-4}	2.170	-33.4	-34.6	-34.0	-34.2
& BaCl ₂	7.003×10^{-4}					
BaCl ₂	8.004×10^{-4}	1.338	-34.1	-33.9	-34.0	-32.7
AlCl ₃	7.180×10^{-4}	1.594	-31.4	-31.3	-31.3	-33.0
CO(NH ₂) ₆ Cl ₃	8.034×10^{-4}	1.309	-32.0	-33.3	-32.6	-32.8

DISCUSSION

The values of ζ_a for stannic oxide sol, in the presence of the equicoagulating concentration of various electrolytes, determined by the electro-osmotic as well as the electro-phoretic methods, in the region of slow coagulation are recorded in Tables I and II. It will be noticed that a plot of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/S$ in each case yields a straight line.

• FIG. 2

This means that $1/\zeta$ and ' m ' in equation (1) remain constant. As the rate of coagulation is the same for all the electrolytes used, it is expected that the average radius ' r ' of the colloidal particles should remain constant, and since for electrophoresis ' m ' stands for χ/ζ , therefore ' χ ' must also remain constant. It is evident from Fig. 2 that the value of ' m ' for electro-osmotic line is greater than that for the electrophoretic line. This is in agreement with theory since ' m ' for endosmosis stands for

$$\frac{3V_1}{V_2} \cdot \chi/\zeta_r,$$

where $3V_1/V_2$ is appreciably greater than unity under the experimental conditions of packing. It will be found from Fig. 2 that the electro-osmotic and electrophoretic lines meet the ordinate at the same point, yielding thereby the same value of $1/\zeta$ and, hence, of ζ , viz., -37 mv. It will be noticed from the data recorded in Tables I and II that for electro-osmosis, the values of ζ_a vary from -22.0 mv to -34.5 mv and for electrophoresis, they exhibit a narrow range of variation only. These data indicate that the effect of surface conductance in depressing ζ_a is greater in endosmosis than in electrophoresis. This effect has also been observed in the cases of other sols like As_2S_3 (*Nature*, 1955, 176, 1080), AgI, Al_2O_3 , etc. by Ghosh and co-workers (*private communication*).

Taking $\zeta = 37$ mv and $m = 2.71 \times 10^{-3}$, the values of ζ_a for electro-osmosis have been calculated for different values of ' S ' from equation (1) and are recorded in column 5 of Table I.

It will be noticed that these values of ζ_0 are in good agreement with those calculated from Smoluchowski's equation for the corresponding values of 'S' and recorded in column 4 of Table I.

Again taking the same value of ζ , *i.e.*, 37.0 mv and $m = 4.51 \times 10^{-7}$, the values of ζ_0 for electrophoresis for different values of 'S' have been calculated from equation (1) and are recorded in column 7 of Table II. Here also a fair agreement is noticeable between these values of ζ_0 and the average of those calculated from electrophoretic data by using Smoluchowski's equation for the corresponding value of 'S'. Furthermore, since the value of true ' ζ ' is the same for all the electrolytes used, it may be concluded that a given rate of coagulation of SnO_2 sol by an electrolyte is characterised by a definite value of true ' ζ ' potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

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